

Chemistry of *Acacia concinna* and *A. caesia* Bark

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ACACIA *concinna* D. C., popularly known as *Shilkakai*, is a prickly scandent bush occurring throughout tropical forests of India. Since its pods are used extensively as detergent, they are often confused with soap-nut (*Sapindus mucorossi*) because of their similar properties¹.

The pods yielded saponin, the saponin of which were characterised as acacic acid lactone, machaerinic acid and its lactone by Anjaneyulu *et al*² in contradiction to the observation of Varshney *et al*^{3,4} who reported only acacic acid.

Certain tribes in Nilgiris (S. India) also use its bark for cleaning hair⁵. Literature survey revealed that no work has been done on the bark, therefore, a systematic chemical examination of this part was undertaken. The bark yielded saponin which was found to possess spermicidal activity⁶.

Acacia caesia Willd., a sister species of *A. concinna* is a large climbing shrub distributed in Gujarat, Konkan and Western Ghats of Bombay to Anamalais⁷. The bark is reported⁸ to yield stigmasterol, a triterpene alcohol and an aliphatic hydroxy compound.

The bark on reinvestigation did not yield any saponin. The absence of saponin would support the contention of Gamble⁹ that *A. caesia* is either one of the varieties of *A. intsia* or a separate species but not synonymous¹⁰ with *A. intsia* which yields¹¹ saponin with acacic acid as the saponin.

Experimental

The powdered bark of *A. concinna* was sequentially extracted with alcohol and *n*-hexane. The alcoholic extract was separated into ether soluble and insoluble fractions. The ether soluble fraction was combined with the *n*-hexane extract and subjected to column chromatography over alumina to yield, *hexacosanol*, m. p. 80°; C₂₆H₅₄O; acetate, m. p. 64°. Identified through mixed m. p., co-TLC and superposable IR spectra; α -*Spinasterol*, m. p. 164-165°; C₂₉H₄₆O (Found: C, 84.79; H, 11.32%. Calcd. C, 84.88; H, 11.22%); ν_{max}^{KBr} 1710, 997 cm⁻¹; MS, m/e 410 (M⁺), 367, 298, 271 and 229, characterised by mixed m. p., co-TLC and superposable IR spectra with an authentic sample and its reduction (LiAlH₄) to α -spinasterol, m. p. 164-165°; *Lupeol*, m. p. 190-192°; C₃₀H₅₀O; M⁺ 426; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3390, 1639, 880 cm⁻¹; acetate, m. p. 210-212°; M⁺ 468, identified as lupeol by direct comparison with an authentic sample in regard to

mixed m. p., co-TLC and superposable IR spectra; α -*Spinasterol*, m. p. 164-166°; C₂₉H₄₆O; M⁺ 412; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3425, 965 cm⁻¹; acetate, m. p. 179-181°; C₃₁H₅₀O₂ (Found: C, 81.80; H, 11.28%. Calcd. C, 81.95; H, 11.01%), confirmed through mixed m. p., co-TLC, superposable IR spectra with an authentic specimen and its oxidation (CrO₃/Py) to α -spinasterone, m. p. 164°.

The ether insoluble fraction on processing yielded an amorphous saponin which on hydrolysis (2% alcoholic H₂SO₄, w/v) gave (i) *Lupeol*, m. p. 189-190°; (ii) α -*Spinasterol*, m. p. 160-162° and (iii) *Acacic acid lactone*, m. p. 254-256°; C₃₀H₄₆O₄ (Found: C, 76.15; H, 10.97%. Calcd. C, 76.55; H, 9.85%); ν_{max}^{KBr} 3663, 3443, 1767, 1650, 980 cm⁻¹; MS, m/e 470 (M⁺), 452, 263, 244, 207, diacetate, m. p. 232-234°; ν_{max}^{KBr} 1780, 1730, 1242 cm⁻¹; M⁺ 554. Acacic acid lactone and acacic acid lactone diacetate were confirmed through mixed m. p., co-TLC, superposable IR spectra with authentic specimens. The sugars were identified through co-PC as glucose, arabinose and rhamnose.

The occurrence of lupeol and α -spinasterol as glycosides was established by running TLC of the saponin against authentic samples of lupeol and α -spinasterol when the plate (TLC) did not show the presence of these compounds in the saponin.

The bark of *A. caesia* on similar processing (*ut supra*) yielded lupeol, α -spinasterol and stigmasterol but no saponin.

Spermicidal activity of the Saponin :

One percent solution of the saponin was prepared in the Sorensen's isotonic phosphate buffer (pH 8.0) containing 17% glucose and 0.38% NaCl for maintaining good sperm motility as recommended by Blackshaw and Emmens¹². The required percentage of saponin was obtained by successive increment of addition of the 0.2 ml of buffer solution. Human semen was diluted to the extent to give an average count of 4-6 motile spermatozoa per high power field (h.p.f.) of microscope. The tests were performed at 37° after every addition of 0.2 ml solution of saponin and after a gap of a minute, the number of motile spermatozoa were counted under h.p.f. of microscope. The maximum activity was observed at 0.004% dilution.

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Hydrocarbons Alcohols and Phytosterols from the Leaves of *Daucus carota*, Nantes**

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LEAVES (900 gm) of *Daucus carota*, Nantes (Umbelleferae) (commonly known as Pahari Gajar) collected from the surroundings of Aligarh district were air-dried, powdered and extracted with hot light petroleum (60-80°). A total of 18.6 gm. (2.06%) extract was obtained, which was subjected to chromatographic separation over neutral activated alumina (30 fold excess).

Elution with light petroleum (60-80°) yielded a colourless waxy product (300 mg), m. p. 57-58° (acetone), TLC-homogeneous (Silica gel-2% AgNO₃). I.R. spectrum indicated the presence of *n*-alkanes with a long chain. This fraction was then analysed by gas liquid chromatography which represented the homologous series of *n*-alkanes C₁₅-C₃₉ with maximum occurrence of C₂₉ (19.8%), C₂₇ (14.3%), C₃₁ (12.6%) and C₃₃ (10.0%) (Table 1). Odd carbon *n*-alkanes

prevailed in higher members only of the series whereas the quantitative preponderance of odd-carbon *n*-alkanes in the lower ones was not so significant¹. Some other hydrocarbons (mono methyl branched) were also present in small amounts².

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF *n*-ALKANES AND FREE ALCOHOLS[†]

No. of C-atoms	<i>n</i> -alkanes %	free alcohols %
15-21	traces	—
22	0.5	1.2
23	0.6	0.3
24	1.4	10.4
25	3.0	1.3
26	4.8	34.8
27	14.3	2.4
28	9.1	41.0
29	19.8	1.6
30	7.4	5.2
31	12.6	—
32	6.1	—
33	10.0	—
34	3.0	—
35	2.3	—
36	0.5	—
37 38,39	traces-	—

[†]According to GLC analysis.

Further elution with light petroleum : benzene (1:1) gave a mixture of alcohols (275 mg). This fraction on GLC analysis exhibited a homologous series of primary alcohols (C₂₃-C₃₀) with maximum occurrence of C₂₈ (4.6%), C₂₆ (34.8%) and C₂₄ (10.4%) (Table 1). Even alcohols prevailed as usual^{3,4}. From this mixture only *n*-hexacosanol, m.p. 77-78° (Lit⁵, m.p. 79.5°) could be crystallised from methanol (TLC-homogeneous). It was characterised by preparation of its acetate⁶ (m.p. 64-65°) and by direct comparison with authentic specimen (m.m.p., co-TLC).

Elution with benzene gave the sterol fraction which on crystallisation from methanol gave shining crystals (200 mg), m.p. 137-40°, TLC-homogeneous (Silica gel-5% AgNO₃, several solvent systems). Spectral data indicated it to be a mixture of sterols which could be separated and identified by combined GC-MS. The trimethylsilyl ethers were found to contain mainly two components with two other minor constituents and were identified by direct comparison of GLC retention

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